

Complexes of Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with Schiff Base derived from 2-Acetylfuranglyoxal and *o*-Phenylenediamine

V. S. SHRIVASTAVA* and G. C. SAXENA

Chemical Research Laboratories, R. B. S. College, Agra-292 002

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The complexes having general formulae $M(PFGA)Cl_n$, where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} ; $PFGA = N,N$ -*o*-phenylenebis(2-furylglyoxalimine); and $n=2$, have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment data, electronic and infrared spectral studies.

A number of papers dealing with the studies of metal complexes of the Schiff bases derived from heterocyclic glyoxalic aldehyde with various aromatic amines¹⁻⁸ appeared in the literature. But the chemistry of *N,N*-*o*-phenylenebis(2-furylglyoxalimine) seems to be comparatively of recent origin. The present paper reports the synthesis and characterisation of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal complexes of the Schiff base,

Experimental

The Schiff base ligand was prepared by the condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine and 2-acetylfuranglyoxal in 1:2 molar ratio in ethanolic medium on a water-bath. The Schiff base *N,N*-*o*-phenylenebis(2-furylglyoxalimine) (PFGA) separated on keeping the solution overnight. It was then filtered and crystallised from ether, m.p. 75°.

Preparation of complexes: The similar procedure was adopted for the preparation of all the complexes, reported herein for the sake of brevity only one reaction in detail.

Bis[*N,N*-*o*-phenylenebis(2-furylglyoxalimine)-manganese(II) chloride]: To an ethanolic solution of $MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (0.38 g, 1.9 mmol) was added an ethanolic solution of Schiff base (0.64 g, 2.0 mmol). The reaction mixture (~50 ml) was refluxed for ~4 h and the light green compound separated upon keeping the solution overnight.

Physical measurements: The molar conductance of the complexes was recorded using a

conductivity bridge and a dip type cell having cell constant 0.5 cm^{-1} . The solution was prepared in acetone and DMF. The magnetic susceptibility measurement was made on a Gouy balance at room temperature. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 grating spectrophotometer in the range 200-4 000 cm^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

The reaction of metal chlorides and ligand (PFGA, $C_{18}H_{12}O_4N_2$) may be depicted as

All the complexes are light green solids and their molar conductance measurements (Table 1) show them to be non-electrolyte⁴⁻⁶.

The magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) values (Table 1) for the complexes are slightly higher than the spin-only value of the respective metal ion complex indicating the spin-free octahedral geometry around the metal ions⁷⁻¹⁰, which are close to spin-only magnetic moment, indicating the paramagnetic nature of the chelates.

Electronic spectra: A general feature of the electronic spectra of these complexes is a shift of absorption bands towards the lower energy side due to nephelauxetic effect. The value of nephelauxetic parameter (β) has been calculated by the method of Jorgenson¹¹ using the relation, $\beta = \nu_{complex} / \nu_{aqu}$. Another parameter, the percentage covalency (δ)¹² has also been calculated for these complexes with the help of the expression,

$$\delta = \frac{(1 - \beta)}{\beta} \times 100.$$

The results are presented in Table 2.

* Present address Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II} SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)					Conductivity mΩ ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ_{eff} B.M.
				Metal	Cl	O	H	N		
1.	[Mn(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂)Cl ₂]	Light green	208	12.36 (12.38)	15.98 (15.92)	48.41 (48.43)	2.75 (2.69)	6.35 (6.28)	0.092 4	5.92
2.	[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂)Cl ₂]	Green	150	13.61 (13.40)	16.45 (16.13)	50.0 (49.09)	2.92 (2.72)	6.75 (6.36)	0.083 0	4.08
3.	[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂)Cl ₂]	Dark green	222	12.09 (12.92)	15.86 (15.81)	48.08 (48.11)	3.06 (2.67)	6.22 (6.24)	0.062 8	2.86
4.	[Cu(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂)Cl ₂]	Light green	229	13.93 (13.88)	14.66 (15.64)	48.06 (47.58)	2.31 (2.64)	6.22 (6.17)	0.072 6	1.86
5.	Ligand (PFGA) C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	Black	75	—	—	62.79 (67.50)	4.04 (3.75)	8.67 (8.75)	—	—

TABLE 2—VALUE OF AVERAGE NEPHELAUXETIC RATIO (β) AND AVERAGE COVALENCY PARAMETER (δ) OF PFGA SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	β	δ %
1	0.86	16.279 0
2	0.84	19.047 0
3	0.70	42.555 0

* As in Table 1.

remains unaltered even on complexation. Three new bands appear in the spectra of the complexes at 560, 420 and 270 cm⁻¹ due to M-N, M-O and M-Cl stretching modes, respectively¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

On the basis of analytical, conductance, magnetic, electronic and infrared spectral data, a structure in which metal ions have six coordination number may be proposed.

TABLE 3—SOME CHARACTERISTIC IR BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF PFGA SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{C=N}$	ν_{C-O-C}	ν_{M-N}	ν_{M-O}	ν_{M-Cl}
1.	[Mn(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂)Cl ₂]	1 620s	1 590w	1 015m	580m	420w	290w
2.	[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂)Cl ₂]	1 610s	1 580m	1 020w	580s	420s	280w
3.	[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂)Cl ₂]	1 610s	1 590m	1 020w	560w	430m	270m
4.	[Cu(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂)Cl ₂]	1 620m	1 590m	1 010m	580s	430m	290m
5.	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂ (Ligand)	1 660m	1 610m	1 010s	—	—	—

m = medium, s = strong, w = weak.

The usefulness of the electronic spectra in ascertaining the nature and bonding involved in these complexes are limited. Taking the free-ion as the standard, the ligand causes a slight red-shift (nephelauxetic effect) of the absorption spectral bands¹³. The magnitude of this shift is dependent upon the change in the inter-electronic repulsion parameters¹⁴. The value of β which is less than one, points towards the very slight incidence of covalency in the metal-ligand bond.

Infrared studies: The ir spectra of the ligand (Table 3) exhibit two strong bands at 1 610 and 1 660 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{C=N}$ and $\nu_{C=O}$ ¹⁵⁻¹⁶. These bands show the negative shift in the spectra of the corresponding metal complexes indicating the involvement of C=N and C=O groups in complexation, whereas the ν_{C-O-C} at 1 010 cm⁻¹

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